

MODELLING OF AUXETIC PARTICULATE-FILLED POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The study uses a Finite Element modelling tool (ANSYS) to optimise the mechanical performance of an adhesive system via the inclusion of auxetic particulate fillers. Modelling results are compared to existing analytical models for filled systems.

Keywords: FEM, auxetic, particulate fillers, adhesive

INTRODUCTION

The study of the micromechanics of heterogeneous materials is useful in order to assess the macroscopic properties, including the effective mechanical properties of the hybrid material. Particle-filled materials are an important class of materials which has attracted a lot of attention from researchers [1][2][3][4][5][6][7][8][9]. The optimisation of the mechanical properties of composites is based on the knowledge of the relationship between the microstructure and macrostructure. Early theories include Voigt [10](1928) who assumed an equal strain approximation in tensile deformation (a parallel connection between matrix and filler). Reuss [11] (1929) developed an expression for an equal stress approximation (series connection between matrix and fillers). The Voigt-Reuss model (Rule of mixtures model) showed that there is an upper and a lower bound for a practical case. Further significant developments made in the sixties include theories by Paul[12] (1960), Hashin and Shtrikman[13][14] (1962, 1963), Hashin and Rosen[15] (1964), and Hill[16] (1965) just to mention a few. The researchers developed the variation methods, the self consistent model methods and exact solutions. These theories are based on the assumption that the effective mechanical properties of a composite are depended on the summation of the behaviour of the elementary particles contained within. The Hashin Shtrikman model takes into account the Poisson contraction of the different constituents of the composite. The H-S bounds are more refined and are not as widely spaced as Voigt Reuss bounds and Paul's bounding methods for systems where the modular ratio of particle to matrix is less than 20[17]. Different particle distribution patterns including cluster [18] or homogeneous arrangement [19] will yield different effective mechanical properties of the composite. It was also observed that the aspect ratio of the particles play a significant role in predicting the Young's modulus, shear modulus and strength of the composite [20][21]. The mechanics of load transfer between constituent materials is complex and should be ultimately verified experimentally.

The present study predicts the performance of a high modulus, positive Poisson's ratio adhesive filled with low modulus, negative Poisson's ratio (auxetic) fillers. Mechanical properties such as Young's modulus are predicted using Finite Element modelling (ANSYS) and the results are compared to existing theories. The effect of the inclusion of fillers with different aspect ratios is also investigated.

METHODOLOGY – ANSYS MODELLING

A simplified model consisting of cubic shaped matrix and filler was explored. The matrix used had a positive Poisson's ratio (conventional), whilst the filler had a negative Poisson's ratio (auxetic). The E_m/E_f ratio (matrix modulus to filler modulus ratio) used in the FE models was approximately 5. The main assumptions made were that (i) the filler and matrix were perfectly bonded; (ii) both filler and matrix were considered to be linear, isotropic and elastic materials. The simplification of matrix and filler shape as well as the assumptions was made for the purposes of this study; however it is known that experimentally it is more complex. Though the results obtained could be an overestimate, they give a good indication of the performance of the filled adhesive composite.

A 3D volume cubic block (1x1x1) was generated. The block was meshed, and the elements were repeatedly copied and generated in the X, Y and Z directions such that a 3D, 15x15x15 elements cube model was obtained. A macro was developed to randomly chose elements and change their properties to the filler, Fig 1a. Care was taken so that double picking of the same cube element was avoided. The total number of picked elements was counted by the software and a volume fraction percentage of fillers was obtained. The properties of the filler and matrix used in the model are shown in Table 1.

Fig 1 Randomly filled adhesive systems: (a) 15x15x15 cubic elements; (b) constant bulk volume model (24x12x6 plate elements); (c) constant element number model (12x12x12 plate elements). Dark elements = filler particles.

A 1% strain was applied in the X direction. Constraints were applied in the U_x and U_y directions. In the post processing section, the reaction loads were determined and the effective Young modulus was calculated from the stress-strain relationships.

Table 1 – Materials properties used

Material type	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Shear modulus (MPa)
Adhesive (matrix)	1700	0.3	615.4
Filler (auxetic)	350	-0.9	1750

EFFECT OF ASPECT RATIO – CONSTANT BULK VOLUME MODEL

The volume of the bulk cube was kept equivalent to a 12×12×12 cube of regular cube elements, but the dimensions of the cube elements were varied to investigate the effect of filler particle aspect ratios. Initially a 1 x 1 x 1 cube was generated, the starting volume was meshed and elements were copied in the X, Y and Z directions such that an equivalent volume to the 12×12×12 block was obtained (Fig 1b). The number of elements for each system increased as the dimensions of the individual cube elements were reduced.

EFFECT OF ASPECT RATIO – CONSTANT ELEMENT NUMBER

The model was constructed as before in ANSYS, keeping the same number of elements, but varying the aspect ratio of each element, Fig 1c. To achieve this however, the shape of the bulk structure changes to a rectangular shaped as opposed to a cube.

ANALYTICAL MODELS

The ANSYS model results were compared to several theories which include bounding techniques of elasticity by Paul[12][22] Hashin-Shtrikman (H-S)[13][14] model and the self consistent field theory[23]. The upper and lower bounds proposed by Paul are based on the principle of minimum potential energy and minimum complementary energy, respectively. The theory assumes that the composite is made up of different isotropic constituents which are uniformly dispersed. The upper bound uses a series of stress strain relations indicated in Equation 1 to obtain the strain energy expression (Equation 2).

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\nu E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} (\varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_z) + \frac{E}{(1+\nu)} \varepsilon_x \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = G\gamma_{xy} = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \gamma_{xy}$$

The strain energy expression is given by Equation 2:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \sigma_y \varepsilon_y + \sigma_z \varepsilon_z + \tau_{xy} \gamma_{xy} + \tau_{yz} \gamma_{yz} + \tau_{zx} \gamma_{zx}) dV \quad (2)$$

The stress-strain expressions of each individual constituent are derived based on their internal strain field and are substituted into the strain energy expression and integrated to give an expression of Young's modulus of the composite in relation to Poisson's ratio of the composite, Equation 3.

$$E_c \leq \frac{1 - \nu_p - 4\nu_p \nu + 2\nu^2}{1 - \nu_p - 2\nu_p^2} E_p V_p + \frac{1 - \nu_m - 4\nu_m \nu + 2\nu^2}{1 - \nu_m - 2\nu_m^2} E_m V_m \quad (3)$$

where ν_p is the Poisson's ratio of the dispersed particles (filler), ν_m is the Poisson's ratio of the matrix, ν is the overall Poisson's ratio of the composite, E_c, E_p, V_p are the Young's modulus of the composite, Young's modulus of the dispersed particles and volume fraction of dispersed particles, respectively.

The Poisson's ratio of the composite is still unknown in Equation 3. By applying the principle of minimum potential energy, strain energy can be minimised in order to specify the bound on E_c . Therefore

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \nu} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \nu^2} > 0 \quad (4)$$

The first derivative is zero when:

$$\nu = \frac{(1 - \nu_m - 2\nu_m^2)\nu_p E_p V_p + (1 - \nu_p - 2\nu_p^2)\nu_m E_m V_m}{(1 - \nu_m - 2\nu_m^2)E_p V_p + (1 - \nu_p - 2\nu_p^2)E_m V_m} \quad (5)$$

The value of Poisson's ratio obtained in Equation 5 is substituted into Equation 3 to get the upper bound on Young's modulus of the composite.

The lower bound is based on the principle of complementary energy. The same stress-strain relations (Equations 1) are used to get an expression of strain energy (Equation 2). The internal stress field and the stresses of equilibrium are determined and substituted into the strain energy equation giving;

$$U^o = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \frac{(\sigma^o_x)^2}{E} \partial V = \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \int_V \frac{\partial V}{E} \quad (6)$$

Since the matrix has E_m over a certain volume V_m and the dispersed particles have E_p over V_p then:

$$\int_V \frac{\partial V}{E} = \int_{V_m} \frac{\partial V}{E_m} + \int_{V_p} \frac{\partial V}{E_p} \quad \text{and} \quad U \leq U^o \quad (7)$$

Hence

$$E \geq \frac{E_m E_p}{V_m E_p + V_p E_m} \quad (8)$$

The self consistent field method is a refinement of the rule of mixtures which uses strain-displacement and constitutive relations. It assumes uniform strain in the two phases of the composite and assumes continuity at interface between the phases. The SCF expressions for Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus of the composite are shown in Equations 9-11.

$$E_1 = V_f E_{1f} + V_m E_m + \frac{4(\nu_m - \nu_{12f})^2 K_f K_m G_m V_m V_f}{K_f K_m + G_m (V_f K_f + V_m K_m)} \quad (9)$$

$$\nu_{12} = V_f \nu_{12f} + V_m \nu_m + \frac{(\nu_m - \nu_{12f})(K_m - K_f) G_m V_m V_f}{K_f K_m + G_m (V_f K_f + V_m K_m)} \quad (10)$$

$$G_{12} = G_{12f} \frac{(1+V_m)G_m + V_f G_{12f}}{V_f G_m + (1+V_m)G_{12f}} \quad (11)$$

where $K = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}$ and $G = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}$

Improved bounds for two-phase materials were obtained by Hashin- Shtrikman (H-S model). The H-S model assumes the composite to be isotropic and linearly elastic. The H-S lower bound on Young's modulus is given in Equations 12.

$$E_c = \frac{9 \left(K_m + \frac{V_p}{[1/K_p - K_m]} + [3V_m/(3V_m + 4G_m)] \right) \left(G_m + \frac{V_p}{[1/G_p - G_m]} + [6(K_m + 2G_m)V_m/5(3K_m + 4G_m)G_m] \right)}{3 \left(K_m + \frac{V_p}{[1/K_p - K_m]} + [3V_m/(3K_m + 4G_m)] \right) + \left(G_m + \frac{V_p}{[1/G_p - G_m]} + [6(K_m + 2G_m)V_m/5(3K_m + 4G_m)G_m] \right)} \quad (12)$$

K and G are the bulk modulus and the shear modulus; and m and p refer to matrix and particle respectively. The H-S upper bounds are determined by interchanging m and p properties.

The lower bound on shear is given by Equation 13.

$$G_{12} = G_m + \frac{V_p}{\frac{1}{G_p - G_m} + \frac{6(K_m + 2G_m)V_m}{5(3K_m + 4G_m)G_m}} \quad (13)$$

Interchanging m and p will give the H-S upper bound on shear modulus.

The upper and lower bounds are widely apart; hence the H-S bounds which are closer together were also used to verify the ANSYS results. The self consistent field (SCF) theory seemed to give an average of all the other theories. The limitations of the theories are known and further work will be carried out experimentally to validate the results.

RESULTS - YOUNG'S MODULUS PLOTS

Auxetic Inclusions

The effective Young's modulus plots are shown in Fig 2. The ANSYS model predicts an increase in modulus of the filled adhesive system up to a peak at approximately 44% filler content, above which the modulus starts to fall. It is interesting to note that the filler is of a lower modulus compared to the matrix. However the filler is auxetic and the negative Poisson's ratio is believed to influence the increase in the effective Young's modulus when the composite undergoes deformation. When tensile strain is applied to the filled system, the matrix tends to contract due to the positive Poisson's ratio whilst the auxetic filler tends to expand, thus restricting the matrix contraction. The reduction in lateral displacement of the matrix is accompanied by a Poisson-reduction in the axial strain on the composite. This observation has also been reported by other researchers [24][25].

The ANSYS model results falls directly on the H-S upper bound. The SCF model predicted values were between the H-S lower and H-S upper bounds (average). The upper and lower bounds were shown to be more widely apart compared to the H-S

bounds. The ANSYS model gives a good approximation since it fall within the H-S bounds. The SCF however seems to give an average estimate of all the results.

Fig 2. Comparison of ANYS results, H-S upper and lower bounds, Upper and Lower bounds and SCF model

Conventional inclusions

Keeping every parameter constant, except that the filler now has a positive Poisson's ratio instead of a negative one resulted in completely different results. The inclusion of a low modulus positive Poisson's ratio filler resulted in a constant reduction in overall Young's modulus of the composite. It was found that as long as the Poisson's ratio of the filler is positive, having extreme Poisson's ratios of the matrix and filler does not have much effect on the effective Young modulus results predicted by the SCF theory, Fig 3. The filler:matrix Poisson's ratio of 0.05:0.45 gave similar results to filler:matrix Poisson's ratio of 0.2:0.3. The simple rule of mixtures is a good estimate for positive Poisson's ratio fillers.

Fig 3 Comparison of auxetic filler to conventional filler

The modelling results obtained from ANSYS for the conventional filler were slightly lower than predicted by rule of mixtures or SCF methods. The conventional filler can be clearly distinguished from the auxetic filler in Fig 3.

Effect of aspect ratio – constant element number model

Fig 4 shows the results for E_x for varying aspect ratio of fillers in the constant element number model.

Fig 4 E_x results for varying aspect ratio (aspect ratios from unity to 100)

The results for E_x show that varying the aspect ratio from unity to 100 has little effect on E_x . For E_y , on the other hand, increasing particle aspect ratio from unity to 20 leads to an enhancement in E_y (Fig 5). There is little further enhancement in E_y as particle aspect ratio increases above 20.

Fig 5 E_y plots – varying aspect ratio (aspect ratios from unity to 100)

Effect of aspect ratio – constant bulk volume model

Fig 6 shows evident enhancement in E_x when aspect ratio is increased. It is noticeable that the enhancement was observed with an aspect ratio as little as two, unlike in Fig 4 where the aspect ratio had to be of the order of 20.

Fig 6 E_x plot- varying filler aspect ratio (aspect ratios = 1, 2 and 4)

Fig 7 E_y plot- varying filler aspect ratio (aspect ratios = 1, 2 and 4)

The plot of E_y is interesting in that varying aspect ratio does not necessarily result in the enhancement of the modulus of the filled system (Fig 7). E_y actually decreases slightly as the aspect ratio is increased.

CONCLUSIONS

The constant element number and constant bulk volume models are idealised models, but they do indicate that we can get an enhancement and introduce anisotropy in the effective mechanical properties by using high aspect ratio fillers. The models presented here do not take into account the possible non-uniform orientation of particles, the interactions between matrix and filler, the packing factor of filler elements etc. Nevertheless, even for the relatively simple FE and analytical model reported here, the predictions suggest benefits that might be exploited by using low modulus auxetic filler within a filled system.

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